

**PROSPECTS FOR THE INTRODUCTION OF DIGITAL BANKING SERVICES IN
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Abstract: Application of new innovative digital technologies in commercial banks in a scientific article. A new approach to creating an innovative new type of product, that is, introducing modern types of services that help customers meet their real needs. Cases of new types of services, that is, in the process of purchasing one product, which allow to use several new types of services, packaging of products with different values, related to the theoretical basis of organizing innovative activities, were considered.

Keywords: Commercial bank, Digital and product strategy, innovative services, information technologies, digital innovative technologies, business model.

Introduction

In the banking system of Uzbekistan, a number of works have been carried out in recent years to improve the quality and scope of banking services. However, the changes taking place in the world, the process of globalization, excessive development of competitiveness, make it necessary to further activate the transformation process of commercial banks, to bring the banking services provided to customers to a new level. In this process, the main goal of reforms in the banking system is to teach commercial banks to work for the client.

From this point of view, the implementation of reforms related to the transformation of the banking system depends on modern, educated personnel, and the fact that the representatives of the banking sector have mastered the effect and essence of the reforms carried out in the banking system is considered one of the main factors.

Based on this goal, this year, the implementation of the tasks set for the wide transformation of the banking system, as well as the introduction of modern models of banking business, requires the use of practical and effective forms of cooperation between the Central Bank and commercial banks. Such an approach serves to build and increase trust in the banking system among the population in the context of a pandemic.

The spectrum of banking services is expanding every year, new types of products and services are constantly appearing on the market. This factor serves to strengthen the competition between credit organizations for each customer. Therefore, each bank builds its relationship with the client based on the principles of partnership. Thus, credit institutions must not only permanently protect their clients' funds, but also contribute to the development of the population's business activities by offering new banking products and services. Banking products and services are evolving under the influence of many economic and social factors.

Analysis of literature on the topic

Research on the needs of customers and their satisfaction in the banking services market, as well as issues such as banking services, Russian scientists E.F.Zhukov[1], O.I.Lavrushin[2], T.N.Nesterova[3], A.N.Ivanov[4], and the French economist. It is reflected in the scientific research of the de Cussers. Peter S.Rose [5] says of the services provided to the public by banks, specifically banks: “a bank is a firm that provides financial services, professionally manages the money of a society, and also performs many functions in the economy”.

In addition Peter S.Rose has conducted research on banking services such as currency exchange, commercial promissory notes and loan provision to businesses, savings deposits, value storage, credit support of government activities, check accounts (deposits until required), trust services, and offering consumer loans that have made their breakthrough in recent years, selling insurance services, selling benefit plans, offering brokerage services on securities transactions.

According to the scientist of this Economist, the change in the form of banking is realized using several main trends: an increase in the number of services, an increase in competition, deregulation, an increase in the cost of financing, funds that are too sensitive to interest rates, technological revolution, consolidation and geographical expansion, globalization of banking, an increase in the risk of bankruptcy and a Russian scientist E.F.Zhukov [6] commented in his tutorial to the banking institution and bank operas: “when the bank is considered as an institution that collects funds and places them on the basis of refunds, it will be possible to distinguish between active and passive operas in its activities”.

According to D. U. Madgazieva, the wide introduction of modern information and communication technologies in the relationship between the bank and the client, including the creation of a mechanism for encouraging the introduction of financial services based on relatively inexpensive digital technologies, 24/7 service equipment (payment terminals,

infokiosks and It is important to offer convenient services for bank customers and residents of our country by dramatically increasing the number of ATMs [7].

According to a group of scientists led by A.R. Norov, today the main activity of commercial banks in the Republic is aimed at introducing innovative banking products. Increased competition due to the pandemic has led banks to introduce the latest business process management technologies, as well as automated decision-making systems [8]. Innovative banking products are an important tool in managing a commercial bank in competitive conditions. Also, innovative banking products and services are important for commercial banks in ensuring economic growth and competitiveness.

Research methodology

Methods such as analytical comparison of tables, logical and comparative analysis of research, grouping of data, statistical processing by comparing them with each other, calculation of quantitative and qualitative indicators were used in conducting scientific research.

Analysis and results

In the process of transformation of banks, it is inevitable that the demands of customers will increase, and as a result of the lack of high-quality provision of advanced innovative banking services in this regard, it may lead to a decrease in the trust of bank customers in their bank. As a result, bank customers tend to switch banks or use other banking services. Therefore, it is necessary to transform the activities of banks according to the requirements of their customers, that is, to create new banking services using modern information and communication technologies. The following are bank products: - creation of payment funds; - providing services. The creation of payment funds is taken at the scale of the entire economy (or, in other words, at the macro level).

As we know, the exchange of labor products is carried out not in the form of exchange of one product for another type of product, but in the form of buying and selling. A producer offers his product to the market. In turn, the buyer will be able to buy the product he needs if he sells his goods. In a market economy, money in the form of common payment funds is needed to carry out the buying and selling process. Without means of payment, there will be no possibility of exchange of labor products between producers of goods. The Central Bank issues funds necessary for the circulation, use and consumption of material assets, as well as for the continuation of the production process.

Banking services, which are the second component of banking products, can be classified as follows (Table 1):

Table 1

Classification of banking services, which are the second component of banking products

Classification criteria		Type of services provided
1.	Depending on the nature of the bank's activity	Specific services Non-specific services
2.	Depending on the subjects served r	Legal entities Individuals
3.	Depending on the method of attracting and deploying bank resources	Active operations Passive operations
4.	Depending on the fee for the services provided	Paid services Free services

In addition, there are non-traditional types of banking services, which include all other banking services. The number of non-traditional banking services is the majority, and some of their manifestations are listed below:

- intermediary services;
- services aimed at the development of the enterprise (i.e. listing, stock placement, legal services, information services and hakazo);
- providing guarantees and guarantees;
- fiduciary operations (including consulting and assistance in managing the client's property on behalf of the client);
- providing accounting assistance to enterprises;
- representation of the client's interests in judicial bodies;
- services for providing safes;
- tourist services and others.

Banking services considered on the basis of the above classification are provided both for clients with the status of legal entities and for individuals. In banking practice, the above set of banking services may be the same in banks, only their scope will be different. When looking at bank services from the point of view of being paid and the bank's income, the following symbols can be added to help provide additional clarity: income-generating and non-income-generating services; expensive and cheap services.

Most of the bank's asset operations provide the bank with an opportunity to earn income, and on the contrary, passive operations, which provide for the payment of interest on savings (deposits), incur costs for the bank. Some banking services require a lot of work, so they are expensive. For example, the service of issuing a letter of credit and its implementation is more expensive for the bank than the service of transferring the client's money based on the payment order.

As we have shown above, depending on the movement of material products, banking services are divided into two types: services related to the movement of material products and pure services. Banks mainly provide services for the movement of material goods with the help of their monetary operations, the main part of which belongs to the first type. These services of the bank that facilitate the movement of goods (for example, transport services to enterprises, communication, trade) create a new additional cost. Net services are provided by the bank directly to enterprises engaged in material production, as well as to certain categories of citizens to meet personal needs. As we mentioned, banking products are various services. Unlike the service of manufacturing enterprises, the banking service does not have a material appearance. Therefore, banking services cannot be stored in warehouses, produced in the form of reserves, unlike material production industries, where the product of labor takes the form of an object. One of the important features of banking services is their production nature.

Even the simple-looking practice of attracting funds of citizens and enterprises to bank deposits has a high production meaning. In this case, the bank not only collects money, but also puts "non-working" funds into working condition. In this way, banking operations cause the development and acceleration of production by serving the economic activities of customers. Another feature of banking services is that large amounts of funds move from one account to another, from one region to another, that is, there is a movement of capital in the form of money. Take, for example, a banking transaction involving lending. It is known that the provided loan must be returned to the bank within the specified period together with additional interest payments.

Conclusions

To sum up, today the banking system should pay special attention to the following issues while accelerating its integration into the global financial market:

1. Changing the way banks operate, developing their own strategy for each client;
2. Critical study of problematic loans during the pandemic, analysis of the financial situation of the bank's clients in remote areas, individual approach to each client;

3. Introducing innovative new types of online provision of high-quality banking services to the population while developing information technologies and communication;

4. Digital banking saves time and costs when providing financial services through mobile and online platforms, ensures the safety of personal data, and increases the speed and quality of service.

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